

Researchers in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "Researchers, FTE/mn pop." within the context of the Global Innovation Index represents the number of researchers in full-time equivalent (FTE) per million inhabitants in a given country or region. This indicator is essential for assessing a country's capacity to generate and sustain innovation, as a higher number of researchers is often associated with a vibrant and productive research environment. Researchers in this context include not only scientists and engineers but also experts in other fields who contribute to the development of new technologies, processes, or knowledge. A higher value in this metric indicates a greater density of professionals dedicated to research, which can suggest a favorable ecosystem for scientific and technological discovery. However, it's not only the number of researchers that matters; the quality of research institutions, available funding, and support for innovation also play significant roles in determining the actual impact of these professionals. Thus, the FTE/mn pop. indicator is used to compare the relative presence of researchers across countries with different demographic sizes, helping to identify nations that invest heavily in scientific human capital and may consequently hold a competitive advantage in the global innovation landscape.

Number of Full-Time Researchers per Million Inhabitants in the Global Innovation Index in 2022. The data on the "Number of Full-Time Researchers per Million Inhabitants" within the context of the Global Innovation Index shows significant variation between countries, reflecting differences in the level of investment in scientific and technological human capital. At the top of the list are countries such as South Korea (100), Sweden (91), Denmark (88.3), and Finland (86.4), which stand out for their strong commitment to maintaining a high density of researchers relative to their population. These numbers indicate an environment favorable to research and development (R&D), a critical

factor in promoting sustainable and competitive innovation. A high number of full-time researchers reflects an institutional and cultural priority in fostering technological and scientific progress, which tends to translate into greater innovation capacity and a knowledge-based economy. In Europe, countries like the Netherlands, Austria, and Switzerland show solid figures, with values of 67.8, 66, and 63.7, respectively, indicating a considerable level of investment in R&D. Countries such as Japan (62.5) and Germany (61.8) rank just below the leaders, yet maintain a substantial number of researchers consistent with highly industrialized and technologically advanced economies. The United States (55.4), while renowned for its strength in innovation, shows a lower value than the Scandinavian countries, suggesting a different distribution of the workforce within R&D sectors and a greater emphasis on private initiatives or specific sectors rather than a high national density of researchers. Italy, with a value of 30.6, is below the European average, suggesting a potential area for improvement in the number of full-time researchers employed. Compared to Western European countries, Italy appears to allocate fewer resources toward strengthening the scientific community and creating structured research environments. This could limit its ability to compete effectively with leading innovation countries, particularly in knowledge-intensive sectors. In developing countries and many emerging economies, the number of full-time researchers per million inhabitants is significantly lower. For instance, countries like Brazil (10), Argentina (14), and South Africa (5.4) show modest figures, while nations such as India (2.7) and Vietnam (8.5) are even less competitive in terms of researcher density. This gap highlights a challenge in implementing adequate infrastructure and resources for R&D, which could enable greater inclusion of these countries in the global innovation landscape. The low number of researchers in these nations may stem from economic limitations, weak policies to incentivize research, or a lack of access to advanced education. Finally, data from African and South Asian countries, such as Ethiopia (0.9), Ghana (0.9), Pakistan (4.2), and Tanzania (0.1), indicate a near-total lack of interest in developing the R&D sector at the national level. This reflects an underlying issue related to resource scarcity and the need to focus investments on other priority sectors such as healthcare and primary education. In these regions, the scarcity of researchers severely limits the potential for innovation, creating a barrier to technological development and improvements in socioeconomic conditions. In conclusion, the indicator “Number of Full-Time Researchers per Million Inhabitants” reflects not only a country’s economic development level but also its priorities in supporting innovation. A higher researcher density tends to correlate with greater innovation capacity and global competitiveness, positioning countries with fewer researchers at a disadvantage compared to advanced economies.

Number of Full-Time Researchers per Million Inhabitants in the Global Innovation Index between 2013 and 2022. Analyzing the data on the number of full-time researchers per million inhabitants within the context of the Global Innovation Index reveals interesting insights into global dynamics of investment in research and development (R&D). The period considered, from 2013 to 2022, shows significant variations in both absolute and percentage terms across many countries, suggesting a shift in national priorities toward strengthening innovative capacities. Countries such as Saudi Arabia, Ghana, and Kuwait recorded impressive increases of 1566%, 800%, and 418% in the number of researchers per million inhabitants, respectively. These increases reflect a growing investment in R&D, often supported by targeted government policies and economic incentives aimed at attracting and retaining scientific talent. In Saudi Arabia, for example, the significant increase can be seen as part of the "Vision 2030" strategic plan, which aims to diversify the economy and reduce dependence on oil, with a focus on innovation. Other countries with notable growth, such as Thailand and Malaysia, which recorded increases of 374% and 361%, respectively, are also intensifying efforts in the technology and research sectors. On the other hand, some countries—primarily those with advanced economies such as Belgium, Germany, and Sweden—showed more moderate percentage increases (below 70%) as they were already starting from a high researcher base. In these countries,

the focus tends to be on improving research infrastructure and the quality of scientific institutions rather than increasing the number of researchers. These increases, while less impressive in percentage terms, demonstrate the strength of existing R&D ecosystems and a commitment to maintaining competitiveness. However, there were also significant decreases in countries such as Iceland, Jordan, and Costa Rica, which saw declines of 30%, 54%, and 34% in the number of researchers per million inhabitants, respectively. These declines may result from a combination of factors, including economic crises, political changes, or insufficient research funding. In Iceland, for example, the decrease could be tied to challenges in maintaining a stable research workforce within a small population, while in countries like Jordan and Costa Rica, the reduction might reflect revised economic priorities or a migration of scientific talent to nations with better career opportunities. Finally, it is noteworthy that emerging economies such as Pakistan, Iran, and Rwanda recorded increases, albeit from a relatively low base. This could indicate a desire to develop local innovative capacities to support the economy and improve international competitiveness. However, without parallel increases in investments in infrastructure and advanced education, these countries may struggle to transform this growth into a real competitive advantage. In conclusion, this data reveals how commitments to research and development vary and respond to different national priorities. Some countries aim to expand the number of researchers to meet future challenges, while others are consolidating already developed ecosystems, ensuring quality and stability.

Conclusions. The value of full-time researchers per million inhabitants grew by an average of 30.85% across the countries analyzed between 2013 and 2022, increasing from 19.56% to 25.72%. The top-performing countries include Saudi Arabia with +1566.66%, Ghana with +800.00%, Kuwait with +418.18%, Thailand with +374.41%, and Malaysia with +361.11%. The worst-performing countries are Uganda with -66.66%, Colombia with -69.23%, Panama with -70.00%, Botswana with -71.42%, and Tanzania with -75%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+46>

Performers	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Saudi Arabia	0,3	5	4,7	1566,667
	Ghana	0,1	0,9	0,8	800
	Kuwait	1,1	5,7	4,6	418,1818
	Thailand	4,3	20,4	16,1	374,4186
	Malaysia	5,4	24,9	19,5	361,1111
Worse Performers	Uganda	0,3	0,1	-0,2	-66,6667
	Colombia	2,6	0,8	-1,8	-69,2308
	Panama	1	0,3	-0,7	-70
	Botswana	7	2	-5	-71,4286
	Tanzania	0,4	0,1	-0,3	-75

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